

RESULT 2 - TRAINING TOOLKITS

To access the documentation related to the justification of the results obtained in relation to *ACTIVITY 2: Development of the training modules*, please click on the following links:

[Result 2 - Training Toolkits](#)

[Module 1 - DIGITAL & SUSTAINABLE ENTERPRISING SKILLS FOR NEETS \(led by HELIXCONNECT\)](#)

[Module 2 - INTEGRATION AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT SKILLS FOR NEETS \(led by ITACA\)](#)

[Module 3 - COMMUNITY-DRIVEN FUNDRAISING FOR NEETS' INITIATIVES \(led by YET\)](#)

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